

FACTORS AFFECTING DEPOSIT OPERATIONS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7176364>

Ayimbetov Abram Dauletbaevich

Nukus, Karakalpak State University

Annotation: *The article reveals the modern features of the mechanism for the formation of the deposit policy of a commercial bank, the factors affecting the effectiveness of the deposit policy, the principles and criteria for the formation of the deposit policy.*

Key words: *deposit policy, accounting, efficiency, contribution, factors.*

Relevance Increasing the efficiency of deposit operations of commercial banks is very relevant and worthy of attention today. In this regard, the issues of increasing the resource potential and ensuring its stability by increasing the efficiency of deposit operations of commercial banks are of particular importance in the current conditions of the banking system.

Deposit operations management are actions aimed at increasing the liquidity of a commercial bank at the lowest cost by seeking borrowed funds, that is, increasing the share of some resources and reducing the share of other funds in the structure of the resource base of a commercial bank, minimizing the share of unstable liabilities [1]. The basis of the tactical management of bank deposit operations is, first of all, the establishment of a clear monitoring of the quantity and quality of its deposit portfolio [2].

The deposit policy of the bank provides for:

- analysis of the deposit market;
- definition of target markets;
- minimization of expenses in the process of attracting funds;
- optimization of the management of the bank's deposit portfolio in order to increase its stability and maintain the required level of the bank's liquidity.

When conducting a deposit policy, the bank takes into account the following factors:

- change of the current legislation;
- the current state and trends of the financial market, both in terms of attracting and allocating resources;
- changes made to the calculation of banking standards;
- change in the refinancing rate of the Central Bank;

volume and cost indicators approved by the bank for ongoing banking (including deposit) operations.

The deposit policy is a tool to attract the optimal amount of financial resources, which further help the bank to develop in other directions. To solve existing problems, when developing a deposit policy, a commercial bank must be guided by certain criteria for its optimization.

Optimization of the bank's deposit policy is a complex multifactorial task, the solution of which should be based on the consideration of the country's economy as a whole.

Obviously, these interests do not always coincide. Therefore, the optimal deposit policy involves first coordinating their interests.

General and specific principles are the basis for the formation of the deposit policy of a commercial bank.

It can be noted that the deposit policy is the main link in the banking policy. The purpose of the deposit policy is to attract as much money as possible at the lowest possible price.

Based on this, its successful implementation involves the solution of a number of tasks in the process of its formation:

- maintaining the level of bank liquidity;
- support in the process of carrying out deposit operations to receive bank profits or create conditions for making profits in the future;
- supplying the diversification of the subjects of deposit operations and the combination of different forms of deposits;
- implementation of a flexible interest rate policy [3].

One of the new forms of increasing the efficiency of deposit operations of commercial banks is the implementation of activities by commercial banks, which provide for the attraction of deposits of individuals and legal entities in the national currency and increasing the level of confidence of legal entities and individuals in the country's banking system. An increase in the number of attracted deposits of individuals and legal entities in the national currency is possible if the deposit in the national currency is linked to a stable foreign currency, which will make it possible to increase the interest of individuals and legal entities in keeping funds in savings, and on deposit accounts in commercial banks.

Increasing the efficiency of deposit operations of commercial banks provides for the improvement of the mechanism for transactions with payment cards for legal entities, which includes:

- 1) an increase in the number of issuers of payment cards, an increase in the number of ATMs and terminals;
- 2) increase in popularity of operations with payment cards among commercial banks;
- 3) establishment of a differentiated fee for balances on payment cards;
- 4) the possibility of providing an overdraft on payment cards to legal entities in the event of their stable economic situation for previous periods and at the present time;
- 5) expanding the range of transactions that can be carried out with payment cards [3].

Thus, from the foregoing, we can conclude that deposit operations are very important for commercial banks, since they are the main source of the formation of the resource base. And the goal of any commercial bank is to find ways to improve the efficiency of deposit operations in order to compete and carry out successful activities in the financial and credit markets. The main goal of the deposit policy of a commercial bank is the formation of the necessary amount of financial resources, which will allow for active operations in the money, credit, foreign exchange and financial markets, taking into account the minimization of the costs of a commercial bank to attract and place funds.

Literature used:

1. Edronova V.N., Mizinovsky E.A. Accounting and analysis of financial assets: shares, bonds, bills / V.N. Edronova, E.A. Mizinovsky. - M.: Finance and statistics, 1995. - 272 p.
2. Rose Peter S. Banking management / Rose Peter S. - Per. from English. - M.: Delo, 2005. - 768 p.
3. N. D. Tkach, O. M. Tkach, and K. Yu. Deposit policy of forming the resource base of a commercial bank.